

Deliverable Report D7.4

Short Interim Management Report

Project & Programme Information	
Project Acronym	INSIGHT
Project Full Name	Integrated Models for the Development and Assessment of High Impact Chemicals and Materials
Grant Agreement No.	101137742
Work Programme	HorizonEurope Cluster 4 - Digital, Industry and Space
Call	RESILIENT VALUE CHAINS 2023 (HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01)
Topic & Title	HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-22: Integrated approach for impact assessment of safe and sustainable chemicals and materials
Instrument	Horizon Europe – Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Project Start Date	01 January 2024
Duration	48 months

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Associated Partners from (a) Switzerland, (b) United Kingdom, (c) Korea, (d) Brazil, (e) Australia, and (f) USA received national funding from (a) the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), (b) Innovate UK (UKRI), (c) The National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF), and (d) the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAESPE).

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Deliverable Information	
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1.1	xx.xx.202x	Update			

¹ R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Acronyms Listed in this Document	
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
DESCA	Model consortium agreement
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
EEAB	External Expert Advisory Board
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement

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Contents

1	The objective for the period	7
2	Progress obtained and outcome	7
3	Issues encounter and challenges to address forward	8

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a short overview (max 5 pages) of the project management actions during the first year.

The deliverable consists of three elements:

- The objectives for the period
- Progress obtained and outcome
- Issues encountered and challenges to address these going forward.

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1 The objectives for the period

The objectives for months 1 to 12 were to focus on managing administrative and technical tasks, establishing all necessary agreements, communication channels, and meeting practices within the consortium. In the first year the aim was to ensure that all processes and systems were in place and to get the work up and running and ensure the smooth and timely completion of all project deliverables due in the 1st year of the project.

2 Progress obtained and outcome

The overall management of the coordination tasks during the first year (M1-M12) was conducted according to the project plan.

INSIGHT Grant Agreement (101137742) was prepared and signed in 12/2023 and the INSIGHT Consortium agreement (based on DESCA I.I. November 2022) was finalised and signed by all the project partners at the beginning of the project.

Pre-financing has been paid to the project beneficiaries at the beginning of the project. Internal financial reports have been gathered from each beneficiary and monitored every six months.

Consortium meetings, WP meetings, case study and framework meetings have been organized regularly. The agendas typically contain a topical theme or status of the progress in each WP. Smaller online meetings for development issues have been organized on demand. The INSIGHT Kick-off meeting was held in Helsinki, Finland on the 15-16 February 2024. All partners were represented and the project got a good start on the team work. A General Assembly and an Executive board, consisting of the WP leaders, were established to ensure proper management of the project. A risk management leader, intellectual property rights (IPR) manager, and an ethics advisor have also been appointed within the project.

The INSIGHT External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) will be appointed and steered by the General Assembly. During the first year of the project, three candidates were selected for the EEAB; Dr. Karin Wiench from BASF Germany, Dr. Thomas Jakl from the Ministry of the Environment of the Republic of Austria and Dr. Vania Vilas Boas from INL Portugal, thereby representing industry, government and academia, respectively. Confidentiality agreements (equivalent to a non-disclosure agreement “NDA”) have been signed by all members. The external advisors are responsible for monitoring the quality of the project. They attend the INSIGHT consortium meetings whenever possible.

To ensure smooth communication within the project, regular meetings are organised with all partners. Direct email is the common means for sharing information and addressing day-to-day

businesses of the project and an INSIGHT mailing list has been created (insight@lists.tuni.fi). An INSIGHT data repository has been created and all partners will be able to share technical documents, written texts, minutes of meetings etc.

During the first year, the first 12 planned deliverables of 35 in total from the INSIGHT project were completed and submitted on time. Five milestones were achieved. The remaining 3 milestones are on track to be achieved according to the project plan.

The quality of the deliverables is being tracked by an internal review process that focuses on scientific merit, consistency and clarity of the document, relevance and coverage of the topic, and language. For each deliverable, 2 partners are assigned as the internal reviewers. This also ensures cross-talk between the work packages.

The first periodical report from INSIGHT will be written according to the project plan covering all activities from months 1-18 (submission is planned in 08/2024).

3 Issues encountered and challenges to address going forward

The management of the INSIGHT project is aligned with the project plan. However, as it is the first year of the project, some practices are still being refined and applied.

INSIGHT faces challenges inherent in its highly interdisciplinary nature. Effective communication among experts from diverse fields is critical yet demanding, especially for the scientific challenge of model and data integration required for different aspects of the SSbD approach. As these experts develop sufficient interdisciplinary domain knowledge, this challenge will be managed more smoothly. The cross-WP meetings focussing on the case studies and the framework have emerged as a means to manage this complexity and ensure effective cross-talk.

